

BorderForce

1st Newsletter autumn 2025

Welcome to the BorderForce newsletter! In this edition, we will introduce the project's scope, objectives, and highlight its initial progress.

BorderForce is an EU-funded project under the Horizon Europe programme. It officially started in November 2024 and will run until April 2027, bringing together leading partners from across Europe to develop innovative solutions for safer, smarter, and more resilient border management.

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What **BorderForce** wants to achieve

Today, 13% of the EU's external land borders are covered by fixed surveillance solutions such as physical barriers. To answer the need for a more flexible green border management, BorderForce is developing mobile, self-sufficient Command and Control (C2) stations that integrate surveillance towers, anti-drone technology, UAVs, and autonomous sensors. With the support of dedicated CubeSat satellites for frequent monitoring of high-risk areas, BorderForce is

setting new standards in real-time border surveillance—while remaining fully aligned with EU fundamental rights and laws.

In the following schema the objectives and the innovation fields are presented, explaining the expected project’s high impact.

[see more](#)

BorderForce Activities

Set the working axes:
Kick-off meeting in Vienna

In November 2024 in Vienna, the BorderForce project was launched with a successful Kick-off Meeting, where all partners came together to establish a shared vision and align on the project's objectives, scope and initial action plan.

This meeting laid the groundwork for effective collaboration and set the path for the upcoming activities aimed at enhancing cross-border security and cooperation based on the following approach.

**Go onto the field:
The BorderForce study visits**

As part of the collection of user requirements from the end-users participating in the project, two visits were organized in **Lithuania** and **Bulgaria**, the countries where the project pilots will take place.

In addition to engaging with the users, the team also visited potential pilot locations, taking into account the varying weather conditions, environments and landscapes. This approach ensures that the BorderForce project addresses the needs of its users—mainly border authorities and customs—in diverse operational settings.

These needs focus primarily on addressing irregular migration and smuggling activities, where the advanced technologies provided by the consortium can make a significant contribution.

The methodology for collecting user requirements included not only technical visits but also close interaction with all participating end-users through interviews and questionnaires. Additionally, technical feasibility assessments and validation by the technology providers supported the drafting of the Pilot Use Cases for system implementation during the pilots.

Study visit to Lithuania January 2025

Study visit to Bulgaria April 2025

Assessing the progress: First Consortium meeting in Tampere

BorderForce first internal assessment took place during its first Consortium Meeting held mid-June in Tampere, Finland, at VTT's premises.

All partners attended, making this gathering a significant milestone for the consortium, enhancing collaboration and establishing the direction for the upcoming project phase. Among other issues, the organization of the tests in an industrial environment, which will take place at the premises of consortium partner Securiton in Germany next November, was also discussed.

During these tests BorderForce prototype will be tested and evaluated in industrial environment demonstrating the efficiency and effectiveness.

The Consortium

The Consortium consists of 16 partners, among which were tech providers, research organizations and end-users, from 13 different countries.

[See all partners](#)

Ethics, Data Protection & AI compliance

BorderForce stands for Ethics, Data, and AI compliance. We recognize the potential challenges that may arise during the project's phases, and we are committed to address them through a range of measures.

[See more](#)

To be followed

Our next Spring issue will tell you more about the requirements work and our first tests in an industrial environment. Stay tuned!

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